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Introduction

The country's investment potential, as well as financial, is influenced by various factors and is characterized by a number of macroeconomic indicators such as economic growth, inflation, consumer demand, employment rate, profit margin, credit rates, and the presence and structure of factors of production, the level of infrastructure development, the competitive advantages of the state, its role in world trade and the international division of labor, etc. The investment priorities of reform and development can provide the further dynamics and competitiveness of the entire economy. The main problem of investment development – the sources of investment.

Active investment activity of enterprises is a guarantee of their stable development and achievement of high results. The volume of investments depends on the material and technical state of enterprises, the availability of resources, the qualitative composition of labor resources, the quantity of products, as well as the level of profitability.

Effective investment activity in any industry is determined by the rational use of investment resources. Formation of investment resources is an important component of the investment and general financial strategy of the enterprise, as well as the initial condition for the implementation of the investment process at all its stages. The main purpose of forming investment resources of an enterprise is to meet the needs for the acquisition of necessary investment assets and to optimize their structure from the point of view of ensuring the effective results of investment activity. Increasing the efficiency of managing investment activities of enterprises is limited by a number of factors, in particular, the conditions of the social and political environment, the level of qualification, etc. Eliminating the negative impact of various factors is a prerequisite for improving the efficiency of investment management and investment attractiveness of the industry. Taking into account the reasons for low investment attractiveness of enterprises allows to objectively evaluate their investment activity. There is no rigid linear sequence of stages of investment activity, caused by the peculiarities of the structure of enterprise management, the size of projects, the limited information.

Materials and Methods

Investment strategy – a set of methods and approaches for the implementation of a financial project. Business tactics directly affect profitability, and payback¹. The work includes updating the technical base, expanding the range of products, innovative technologies, improving the skills of personnel, etc. Often, companies prefer a complete reorientation of their activities in order to gain a new market environment.

The essence's concept of a long-term investment strategy is to choose the conditions for financing a specific object to improve the rating among competitors and in the economic market. When the

¹ Khazanovich E. S. Investment strategy: a textbook / E. S. Khazanovich, A.M. Anzhuli, A.V. Moiseev – M.: Knorus, 2010. - 304s.

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organization conducts targeted spending of finances, increases the rate of output, the investor receives the expected income and continues to stimulate the project.

It is important to justify the feasibility and economic benefits of the investment program. Professional analysts and financiers participate in the process. They calculate basic indicators, indexes for a superficial analysis of the prospects for making a profit. The task of the investor and the head of the company is to choose the option of spending funds on the project in comparison with alternative schemes.

The investment strategy of a production enterprise is a kind of master plan, which outlines priorities, a sequence of actions, and an unified system for the development of the object. In simple terms, financing tactics are a model for achieving positive results through the correct allocation of monetary resources. This concept defines the long-term development plan of the company, the specifics of its activities.

The objectives of the preparation and application of the investment strategy are to calculate in detail the percentage of asset allocation by the object's management zones, strategic units, and investment areas². If the finances are spent without a clear plan, the company and the investor will face a loss and a financial crisis in the near future. Tactics are aimed at defining tasks, preparing effective ways to overcome emerging problems.

The basic reasons why an organization makes a decision to attract third-party capital are restoration, expansion of production activities, and access to a profitable level of work. Let's list the objectives of the investment strategy:

- stabilization of the financial situation, growth of basic indicators;
- ensuring the planned growth rate;
- minimizing potential financing risks;
- detailed analysis, study of market conditions;
- technological progress, modernization, introduction of innovations;
- creation of an investment portfolio, ensuring high liquidity of assets;
- detailed assessment of investment instruments, exclusion of unprofitable areas;
- expansion, reorientation of the business due to the received profit;
- reaching a yield of more than 50%, improving the rating and strengthening the business reputation of the company.

The most important step in the investment planning process is the preparation of an action plan³. The development of a new investment strategy is given the maximum possible amount of time. If the experts are wrong in their calculations, it will be very difficult, almost impossible, to return the situation to its original position.

The relevance of developing in a detailed action plan is determined by the following factors:
intensity and aggressiveness of changes in the internal and external economic environment;
combining the activities of different structural divisions of the enterprise to create a single model of a successful business;
features of the formation of investment resources, profitability potential;
implementation of new commercial and production opportunities;

² Investing. Management of investment processes of innovative economy: textbook.- method. Manual for the preparation of masters in the direction of "Economics" / author's collective: L. S. Valinurova, O. B. Kazakova, E. I. Iskhakova. - Ufa: BAGSU, 2012. - 77 p.

³ Teplova, T. V. Investment : textbook. for bachelors

systematization of several investment programs to achieve the set goals (Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Development of an investment strategy

The formation of an investment strategy is a very long and complex process. As a result of the painstaking work of analysts, an ideal investment mechanism is created. Thanks to it, the subject of financial investments conducts short-term business planning, optimizes the asset management process.

The stages of developing an investment strategy directly depend on the aggressiveness and variability of the environment, the market situation. There are five basic points for creating a single tactic:

- formulation of the company's general policy, priorities, and goals;
- detailed analysis of the current market situation, the external environment, and the activity of competitors;
- formation of investment policy;
- preparation of the mechanism for the application of the financing program, starting from the initial investment and ending with the allocation of resources;
- creation of a system of analysis, methods of evaluation actions based on the results of the implementation of the investment project. Importance in the investment activity of enterprises belongs to the regulatory policy of the state.

Recognizing the important role of the state in the transitional (transit) economy, it is important to find the optimal combination of direct and indirect regulatory methods that would, on the one hand, stimulate priority areas (spheres, industries, production) and, on the other hand, minimally harm competition.

Experience of other countries shows that one of the most important areas to improve the financial mechanism of investing innovation in times of crisis is, above all, increased regulation of capital investment on the part of the state, which is accompanied by a reprioritization of public investment and improving procedures requires the allocation of budget funds to implement certain strategic priorities, creating conditions of economic restructuring on the basis of innovation based on existing scientific, technological and innovation capabilities.

State regulation of investment activity of enterprises is implemented through the application of economic, organizational and legal instruments. Under economic methods, we understand the combination of tax, credit, depreciation, innovation, pricing policies, as well as policies for the formation of human capital. Ensuring reproduction of fixed assets at enterprises is the main function of depreciation policy. The amortization policy should be directed at restoring the material-resource base of the enterprise, technological re-equipment by introducing the results of scientific and technological progress. In our opinion, it is expedient to implement amortization policy by the proportional growth of depreciation rates to increase the market value of depreciated facilities. Enterprises should independently form a depreciation policy taking into account the specifics of their own activities.

In the economically developed countries of the European Union, there is a well- developed credit

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system that stimulates the effective development of credit relations and credit provision. The situation in agriculture is indicative. Thus, the countries with the highest share of debt in the agrarian capital include England and Germany – about 50%, France – more than 40, Italy and Belgium – more than 30%. In EU countries, 40% of farms depend entirely on attracting borrowed funds and only 25% of farms do not have bank loans.

In order to improve the credit policy and improve the financial security situation, long-term loans should be granted to producers on a preferential basis. At the expense of loans received at reduced interest rates, they will be able to carry out technical and technological re-equipment of production and significantly increase the volume of competitive products.

In particular, in order to intensify the investment activity of enterprises at the state level, it is necessary to implement the following measures: to support individual bank programs with low interest rates on long-term loans; with the help of state regulatory policy, to help terminate the start of repayment of such loans for the third or fourth year of their use.

Along with the long-term need to promote the development and short-term bank lending. Long-term and short-term bank lending should contribute to the development of investment activities of enterprises. It should be noted that production mainly requires the attraction of long-term bank loans, but the use of short-term bank loans is more affordable, which can not but affect the overall economic situation in one or another industry. In this regard, it is necessary at the state level to implement a policy of cheapening loans. Release due to the mechanism of cheapening short- and long-term lending by partial compensation by the state of the rate on a producer loan part of the funds, along with other investments, should be aimed at improving the conditions of production.

Thus, the issue of lending to producers, which is the source of their investment activity, is always open, and an important role in its solution belongs to the state. After all, the provision of substantiated loans to enterprises allows not only to upgrade the material and technical base but also to stimulate the process of innovation.

Should be underlined that the investment strategy does not function separately, it is an integral, inseparable part of the business plan. Only a close link between social, economic, production and financial policies will preserve production and bring it to a profitable level.

Conclusion

Investment strategy in the period of digital economy is a detailed action plan for financing participants. The model allows you to optimize the process of managing your business, capital, and profitability. It does not contradict the general goals; it is an integral part of them. The investment will be successful and will pay off quickly if the developers take into account all the nuances of the business project, external factors, and the market situation.

In this article, we have reviewed the main investment strategies for novice investors, as well as those who are willing to devote more time and effort to the market. In any case, the strategy is based on individual goals and preferences, which you determine yourself or with the help of your investment adviser.

Thus, activation of investment activity of enterprises is possible provided that a favorable investment climate in the industry is created, that is, an environment formed by the influence of political, economic, social and other factors that determine the conditions of investment activity in the state and the degree of risk of investing in the industry. Support for investment processes of enterprises should become one of the priorities of state policy in order to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of domestic production of goods (works, services). Applying different mechanisms

of state regulation of investment activity, one should take into account the level of development of the national economy, the state of the scientific and technical sphere, the legal basis, the level of risk and objectives, interests and requirements of investors, flexibly combining the above components among themselves.

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